

Structural analysis of the oxyluciferin emitting species in aqueous and luciferase media

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Abstract

Understanding the biological environment that surrounds the fireflies' bioluminescent chromophore is crucial to unravel the key factors that lead to the fine tuning of the emitted radiation. In this work we used the recently published OLU Force Field (OLUFF) to sample the conformational space of the four possible oxyluciferin emitters in both the ground and first electronically excited states in aqueous media and inside the luciferase enzyme to describe the solvation and interaction with the protein. It is shown that, in an aqueous solution, the degree of solvation agrees with the magnitude of the atomic charges on the electronegative heteroatoms for both biological environments. However, in the enzymatic environment, the hydrogen bonding pattern with solvent molecules changes because it competes with direct hydrogen bonds with the protein and the adenosine monophosphate co-factor. These interactions can also be facilitated in some cases via hydrogen bond bridging through water molecules.

Introduction

Bioluminescence consists on a series of biochemical reactions that transform a substrate, typically called luciferin, into an emitting chromophore. This biological process is catalyzed by a protein denominated luciferase. Specifically, in the case of fireflies' bioluminescent system, the mechanism consists on a four-steps reaction of D-luciferin with one oxygen and one adenosine triphosphate (ATP) molecules as reactants that leads to the formation of the oxyluciferin (OLU) molecule in the first electronically excited state.¹⁻⁹ Despite the extensive research on the system¹⁰⁻¹⁴ that has been carried out by the scientific community since the first studies in 1917 by Harvey¹⁵ and the publication of the first crystalline structure of the luciferase protein by Bitler and McElroy in 1957,¹⁶ the exact factors that affect the colour of the emitted light are still unclear. Nonetheless, it has been demonstrated that the excited-state pathways of firefly oxyluciferin implicate more than one emissive chemical form,¹⁴ thus it is of great relevance to understand how each of the four possible emitting species, shown in Figure 1, behaves in different environments in order to be able to efficiently tune the emission properties and improve the already high applicability of the system.

Scheme 1: Chemical structure of the four possible OLU emitters.

Among the oxiluciferine/luciferase applications, they should be pointed out the monitoring of mitochondrial functioning,¹⁷ cancer detection,¹⁸⁻²¹ the study of different agents on cell proliferation and cytotoxicity²² for the detection of contamination of sterilized environments,^{23,24} and bioimaging. This latter application is employed to the analysis of reporter

genes,^{25,26} cell tracking, study of neurodegenerative diseases^{27–32} and analyze protein–protein interactions.^{33–37} All of these applications rely on the participation of ATP in the bioluminescent reaction.^{1–9} Some of these applications not only require the light emission but also a specific wavelength of the emitted electromagnetic wave since a red light is able to penetrate deeper in the tissues and, as aforementioned, the structural properties tuning the emitted colour are yet to be discovered.

This work aims to shed some light not only into the structural behavior of the four possible emitting chromophores in two different environments, an aqueous solution and the inside the enzyme, and in two different electronic states, the ground state S_0 and the emitting state S_1 , but also on the effect of the protonation and electronic state of the OLU on its chemical environment. We have found that the solvation around the different electronegative atoms of the system, which can act as hydrogen bonding acceptors, is related to their atomic charges and is larger in the S_1 than in the ground state, consistently with previous results.^{9,38} Moreover, in the enzymatic media, the solvation is reduced due to the limited amount of water molecules inside the active site. In addition, the presence of direct hydrogen bonds with either the protein or the adenosine monophosphate (AMP) co-factor further reduces this solvation although, this effect competes with the possibility of having bridging water molecules between the chromophore and its chemical environment.

Computational Details

This study was carried out for the four possible oxyluciferin emitters in both the ground and first electronically excited states in two different media, an aqueous solvation and within the luciferase environment, by means of classical molecular dynamics (MD) simulations based on potential gradients computed by the OLUFF.³⁹ The computational details of all these calculations are explained below.

System setup

On the one hand, the optimized structures of the OLU chromophores in each electronic state were taken from a previous study³⁹ and solvated with a truncated octahedral box of water molecules that ensures a solvent shell of at least 20 Å from any solute molecule. Moreover, Na⁺ cations were added to the simulation box to neutralize it (one ion in the case of phenolate-keto and phenol-enolate and two ions in the case of the phenolate-enolate systems).

On the other hand, each of the OLU/luciferase complexes was built from the X-ray diffraction structure file of the Japanese firefly luciferase (PDB ID: 2D1R⁴⁰), *Luciola cruciata*, with PyMol⁴¹ by replacing the structure of the crystallized OLU by that of each of the chromophores under study and modifying the AMP residue as to achieve a net charge of -1 by adding the corresponding H atoms missing in the crystallographic structure, that would correspond to its biological state.^{42,43} Consecutively, the system was solvated and protonated using the *tleap* module of AmberTools22⁴⁴ with water molecules within a truncated octahedral box, ensuring a solvent shell of at least 12 Å from any solute molecule. Moreover, the system was again neutralized by adding Na⁺, the same amount as in the case of the aqueous media since the protonation state of the protein accounts for the negative charge of the AMP.

For both media, the water molecules and Na⁺ cations were described by means of the TIP3P force field,⁴⁵ whereas the OLUFF³⁹ was employed to describe the different chromophores in their respective electronic states. Additionally, the enzyme was described using the ff19SB⁴⁶ force field. As for AMP, the General Amber Force Field (GAFF)⁴⁷ was used to describe the dihedral and improper torsions and Lennard-Jones parameters selected by means of the Antechamber *parmchk2* module of the AmberTools22, while the rest of the bonded parameters and the charges were obtained from QM calculations performed *in vacuo* at the B3LYP/6-31G* level of theory^{48–53} and the Merz–Singh–Kollman scheme⁵⁴ for the atomic charges using the Gaussian09⁵⁵ software. Specifically, the geometry optimization directly provided the equilibrium distances and angles and the force constants were calcu-

lated by means of the Seminario method that consist on the block diagonalization of the QM Hessian matrix of the rows and columns of the atoms involved in a specific harmonic potential.⁵⁶

Classical molecular dynamics

Consecutively to the system preparation, classical MD simulations were performed for each of the 16 prepared systems (4 chromophores in the S_0 and S_1 states in water and protein environments) using the same computational protocol and the CUDA version of the software Amber22.^{44,57-59} First, the system was minimized for 5000 steps by means of the steepest descent algorithm,⁶⁰ and for additional 5000 steps using the conjugate gradient algorithm.⁶¹ Then, it was progressively heated for 500 ps from 0 to 300 K in the NVT ensemble using a 2 fs timestep and an additional simulation was evolved at 300 K for another 500 ps in the same ensemble. The temperature was controlled by means of the Langevin thermostat⁶² with a 2.0 ps^{-1} of collision frequency. Afterwards, a production of 1 μs with a 2 fs timestep and within the NPT ensemble was performed at 300 K and 1 atm. The temperature was also controlled by means of the Langevin thermostat with a 1.0 ps^{-1} of collision frequency and the pressure by means of the Berendsen barostat.⁶³ The particle-mesh Ewald⁶⁴ method was used to compute the electrostatic interactions with a grid spacing of 1.0 \AA , and the non-bonded interactions were computed with a cutoff of 13 \AA and a switching distance of 11 \AA . The bonds involving hydrogen atoms were constrained using the SHAKE⁶⁵ algorithm. Exceptionally, the trajectory for the phenolate-keto chromophore in the S_1 state in the enzymatic medium was evolved up to 1.4 μs to ensure that the protein structure was completely equilibrated, as it can be observed in Figure S1. Finally, the different structural analysis performed in this work have been carried out using the *cpptraj*⁶⁶ module of AmberTools22 by taking into account the 1 μs production in the case of the aqueous simulations and the last 600 ns of the MD trajectories in the case of the OLU/luciferase complex, in order to have an equilibrated structure for the protein. Example *tleap* and MD inputs and the set of

parameters employed for the AMP can be found in the SI of this paper. In addition, all the necessary files to reproduce the simulations can be found in the Zenodo repository DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.15132416.

Results and discussion

As mentioned above, this work aims to explain the behavior of the four possible OLU emitters of fireflies' bioluminescent system in two different biological media and electronic states. Thus, the results obtained in solvent and the protein are discussed separately and, then, compared in the latter section.

Aqueous trajectories

Structure of the OLU chromophores

In aqueous solvation, all the OLU chromophores present a large freedom of movement around the C-C single bond connecting both rings. This can be observed in Figure 1(A,B), which represents the probability distribution for the SCCS dihedral angle, the only torsional degree of freedom that is truly able to rotate. On the one hand, ground state simulations show that the keto tautomers mostly present a s-trans planar configuration (around 180°) for this dihedral angle, although the distribution for the neutral form (phenol-keto) is wider than for the monoanion (phenolate-keto). Moreover, the two enolate species present a non-planar distorted configuration with maxima at 144 and 216° and 132 and 228° for the phenol-enolate and phenolate-enolate OLU, respectively. This is not a surprising result considering that the OLUFF is specifically parameterized to reproduce this behavior.³⁹ In fact, all the SCCS probability distributions, represented in Figure 1, show similar results to those obtained in *in vacuo* from our previous work. On the other hand, S_1 simulations show a different picture for all the chromophores with the exception of the phenol-keto OLU for which the distribution just becomes narrower. While the phenolate-keto chromophore in the excited state is also

able to populate conformations for which the thiazole and benzothiazole moieties are perpendicular to one-another (90 and 270°), both enolate forms are trapped in a planar s-trans configuration. Thus, in the excited state the phenolate-keto OLU presents the larger mobility among the studied systems, as also reflected by their respective root mean square displacement (RMSD) shown in Figure S2.

Figure 1: Probability distributions of the SCCS dihedral angles of each of the OLU chromophores in the (A) S_0 and (B) S_1 electronic states in aqueous media.

Aqueous solvation of the OLU chromophores

When analyzing the solvation around the different OLU chromophores, it can be observed in Figure 2 that the trend of the radial distribution function (RDF) between the chromophores and water molecules in both electronic states coincides with the total charge of the chromophore and the atomic charge on the analyzed heteroatom, taken from the OLUFF. In the case of the RDF around the oxygen atom of the benzothiazole moiety in the S_0 state (Figure 2(A)), the phenolate-enolate (with a total charge of -2 and a atomic charge of -0.724 on the O of the benzothiazole moiety) presents the largest RDF followed by the phenolate-keto (with

a total charge of -1 and an atomic charge of -0.623 on the O of the benzothiazole moiety). In addition, the phenol-enolate and phenol-keto OLUs (with atomic charges of -0.531 and -0.498 on the O of the benzothiazole moiety, respectively) are the chromophores with the lowest RDFs. The O of the thiazole moiety (Figure 2(C)) follows the same trend since both the phenolate-enolate and phenol-enolate (with atomic charges of -0.734 and -0.696 on the O of the thiazole moiety and total charges of -2 and -1, respectively) present the largest RDF while the keto OLUs present a much lower RDF. In the case of the simulations on the S_1 state (Figure 2(B)), a similar result can be observed for the solvation around the O of benzothiazole moiety. However, there is a significant decrease in the solvation around the thiazole O atom for all the chromophores, as seen in Figure 2(D), with the exception of the phenolate-keto (for which the RDF is larger than in the S_0) leading to a similar solvation to that of the two enolate chromophores. This result is due to the fact that it is the only OLU that presents a more negative atomic charge on the thiazole O atom upon excitation. Moreover, the RDF around the two N atoms are not only very similar for all the emitters in each electronic state but also less relevant in comparison to those of the O atoms.

Figure 2: Radial distribution function of the O atoms from water surrounding each of the X four electronegative sites of each of the OLU chromophores in the (A,C,E,G) S_0 and (B,D,F,H) S_1 electronic states in aqueous media.

In agreement with the RDF results, and as it can be observed in Figure 3, hydrogen bonding analysis using the default *cpptraj* angle and distance cutoffs (135° and 3.0 \AA) between the hydrogen bonds donors and acceptors show that the larger the total negative charge of the molecule, the higher the total number of hydrogen bonds with the aqueous environment for all the studied hydrogen bond acceptors. This is not surprising considering that hydrogen bonding has an important electrostatic nature.⁶⁷ Comparing S_0 and S_1 hydrogen bonding patterns, it can be observed that most systems present a decrease in the total amount of hydrogen bonds in the S_1 state due to a decrease in the number of hydrogen bonds created between the solvent and the O atom of the thiazole moiety. This effect is especially stressed in the case of the phenol-enolate chromophore since, for the phenol-keto and the phenolate-enolate the decrease in the hydrogen bonding with the O is slightly compensated with an increase in the number of hydrogen bonds with the N atom of the benzothiazole moiety. Moreover, in the case of the phenolate-enolate OLU, the other N atom also presents

a significant increase in the number of hydrogen bonds. In the case of the phenolate-keto emitter, a slight increase in the total number of hydrogen bonds can be observed when going from the S_0 to the S_1 due to an increase of the hydrogen bonding around both the O atom of the thiazole and the N atom of the benzothiazole moieties. The former is caused due to the fact that it is the only chromophore for which the FF charges of the thiazole O are more negative in the S_1 than in the S_0 , while the latter is a general effect for all the OLU species, since all of them presents an increase in the atomic charge of this N atom upon excitation.

Figure 3: Average number of hydrogen bonds (HB) of each of the OLU chromophores with water and with each of the four electronegative atoms in the (A) S_0 and (B) S_1 electronic states in aqueous media.

Trajectories of the OLU/luciferase complex

Structure of the OLU chromophores

In aqueous media the chromophores are allowed to move and rotate freely, but within the active pocket of the enzyme one could expect that this movement is constrained due to different factors such as steric hindrance and enzyme-substrate interaction. Thus, the structural

properties of the OLU should be affected by the biological media in which it is embedded. While in aqueous media the chromophores were able to rotate around the SCCS dihedral angle, this torsion is not accessible inside the pocket. As can be seen in Figure 4, most of chromophores adopt a s-trans conformation (with a SCCS dihedral angle around 180°) specially for the S_1 state. Exceptions to this arise in the S_0 trajectories. The phenol-keto OLU, that presents a s-trans conformation at the beginning of the production of the trajectory, rotates around this torsion angle within the first 400 ns of the simulation; which, as previously mentioned, are not considered for the analysis since the trajectory need to be equilibrated; and is from then on trapped in the s-cis conformation, with a SCCS dihedral angle around 0° . This motion is mediated by three water molecules and different hydrogen bonding with the surroundings of the chromophore, as explained in the SI. Moreover, the phenolate-enolate is forced into one of the two distorted conformations shown in aqueous media (that around 127°) and the phenol-enolate, in contrast with the aqueous situation, presents a wide distribution that corresponds to a planar s-trans conformation.

Figure 4: Probability distributions of the SCCS dihedral angles of each of the OLU chromophores in the (A) S_0 and (B) S_1 electronic states in the enzymatic environment.

The role of water molecules

When analyzing the solvation of the chromophores within the active site, the first evident difference with respect to the solvated systems in absence of the protein is the restricted amount of water molecules inside the pocket, which led to RDFs one order of magnitude less intense than those in solvent, as seen in Figure 5. The RDF of water molecules around the different heteroatoms of the OLU species in the protein present some additional differences that can be explained by taking into account the nature of the system. The RDF around the O atom of the thiazole moiety of S_0 enolates is lower than in aqueous media (Figure 5(C)). In the case of the phenolate-enolate, this is due to the hydrogen bonding with both the AMP co-factor (Figure 10(C)) and the LYS531 (Figure 8(A)) - numbering referred to that of the 2D1R PDB, while the phenol-enolate only presents hydrogen bonding with the protein (SER201, HIE247 and LYS531) though this hydrogen bond acceptor. Moreover, the complete lost of solvation around the thiazole O atom of the phenolate-keto is due to the high amount of hydrogen bonding with the AMP co-factor. In the RDF around the O atom of the benzothiazole moiety of S_1 (Figure 5(B)) it can be observed a relative decrease for the neutral OLU and the two enolates with respect to the phenolate-keto chromophore that can be explained with the hydrogen bonding with the protein, specifically with the ARG339 in the case of the dianion and with SER316 in that of the to phenol forms (Figure 8(B)). Additionally, not only the RDF around the O atom of the thiazole moiety of S_1 is lower than in aqueous media in general for all the chromophores, but also the ordering for the three anionic forms, which are the ones with a relevant contribution in both media, is reversed (Figure 5(D)). While in water the phenolate-enolate dianion presents the highest RDF and the phenol-enolate the lowest, inside the protein the chromophores with the largest and smallest RDF are the phenol-enolate and phenolate-enolate OLU, respectively. In the case of the phenolate-enolate OLU, the RDF decrease is caused by hydrogen bonding with both ALA350 and SER349, while the phenolate-keto presents some hydrogen bonding with the co-factor and the HIE247. Moreover, the phenol-enolate presents bridging water molecules

between the O atom of the thiazole moiety and THR345, GLY318, HIE247 and the AMP co-factor that might be stabilizing the water molecules around this hydrogen bond acceptor (Figure 9(B)).

When comparing the RDF around the N atoms for the S_0 simulations with respect to the aqueous situation, it can be observed some loss of solvation around them due to a restricted amount of water molecules, which prefer to form hydrogen bonds with the O atoms. Nonetheless, it can be seen some retention of the solvation structure of phenolate-keto and phenol-enolate species in the S_0 (Figure 5(G)) due to water bridging with SER316 (Figure 9(A)) and AMP (Figure 10(E)), respectively. This results will be explained in detail in a later section. In the case of the S_1 simulations, the RDF around the N atom of the benzothiazole moiety (Figure 5(F)) is maintained for all the chromophores but for the phenolate-keto, which is the only one that does not present bridging water molecules with the protein through this atom (Figure 9(B)). Furthermore, in the case of the solvation around the N atom of the thiazole moiety in the S_1 trajectories (Figure 5(H)), only the phenolate-enolate OLU retains a significant solvation. Moreover, the presence of few bridging water molecules between the AMP and the N atom of the thiazole moiety of the phenol-enolate chromophore leads to a small retention of the solvation structure in the form of a very small peak in its RDF.

Figure 5: Radial distribution function of the O atoms from water surrounding each of the X four electronegative sites of each of the OLU chromophores in the (A,C,E,G) S_0 and (B,D,F,H) S_1 electronic states in the enzymatic environment.

Using the same reasoning than for the RDF, the discrepancies between the number of hydrogen bonds in aqueous media and inside the cavity of the protein can be explained (Figure 6). As aforementioned, the limited amount of water molecules inside the active sites reduces the total number of hydrogen bonds with water for all the studied systems inside the enzyme and the difference in the trends for the chromophores in each electronic state can be rationalized with the direct hydrogen bonding with the protein and the presence of bridging water molecules with either the protein or the AMP co-factor. While the presence of direct hydrogen bonding with the protein reduces the amount of hydrogen bonds with the water molecules, the possibility that water acts as a hydrogen bond bridge produces the opposite effect. This will be analyzed in detail later.

Figure 6: Average number of hydrogen bonds (HB) of each of the OLU chromophores with water and with each of the four electronegative atoms in the (A) S_0 and (B) S_1 electronic states sites in the enzymatic environment.

OLU/luciferase interactions

To quantitatively assess the interactions between the different OLU chromophores in both electronic states and the protein, the amino acids with a larger amount of total contacts per residue (native and non native) with the OLU species have been identified by means of the *nativecontacts* command implemented in *cpptraj* using a distance threshold of 5.0 Å. Figure 7 represents the total amount of contacts for those amino acids that present at least 50 contacts with one of the studied chromophores, thus including only the relevant amino acids. On the one hand, S_0 trajectories (Figure 7(A)) show that the most relevant amino acid in terms of number of contacts with the chromophores is the PHE249. Moreover, ILE353, ALA350 and GLY341 also have a similar amount of contacts with all the systems, although in a lower quantity. Furthermore, both enolate forms, and also the phenol-keto OLU to a lesser extent, present a significant amount of contacts with SER349, LEU344, GLY343, TYR342

and GLY341, for which the phenolate-keto chromophore presents a much lower amount of contacts. Additionally, GLY318 presents a significant amount of contacts with both enolate forms; THR253 with the phenolate-keto OLU, and PHE252 and ARG220 with the two phenolate anions. On the other hand, S_1 (Figure 7(B)) presents a different picture. While PHE249 still presents the highest amount of contacts with most of the studied chromophores, this is not the case for phenolate-enolate OLU, for which the number of contacts with this amino acid and with ALA350, SER349, LEU344, GLY343, TYR342, GLY341 and GLY318 is reduced in favor of contacts with ILE353, ARG339, TYR257, THR253, ASN231 and ARG220, leading to a somehow more polar environment. Phenolate-keto OLU also presents a different contacts pattern, favoring the contacts with SER349, LEU344, GLY343, TYR342 and PHE249 to the detriment of ILE535, ALA350, ARG339, THR253 and specially TYR257 and ARG220, which means a local environment with more hydrophobic and aromatic amino acids. Nonetheless, the two phenol forms, present a more similar contacts pattern with respect to the S_0 . In the case of the phenol-keto OLU the most important amino acids are still ALA350, SER349, GLY343, TYR342, GLY341 and the already mentioned relevant PHE249. However the number of contacts with ILE353, ARG339, PHE252, ASN231 and ARG220 is slightly reduced, and with GLY318 slightly increased. For the last of the chromophores, the phenol-enolate OLU, the number of contacts with ALA350, SER349, LEU344, GLY343 and PHE240 is not affected by the electronic state of the molecule while those with TYR342, although still significant, are reduce together with those with GLY341 and GLY318. In general terms, for all the studied systems in both electronic states, the most significant amino acid in terms of contacts is PHE249. The only exception to this would be the phenolate-enolate in the S_1 for which the reduction in contacts with PHE249 is compensated with an increase in contacts with other amino acids leading to a local environment of a higher polarity. In the case of the phenolate-keto OLU, the change of contacts from the S_0 to the S_1 state leads to more hydrophobic pocket with more aromatic amino acids. Finally, both phenol forms present a similar environment in both electronic states since differences

in contacts between them are very small. .

Figure 7: Contacts between the four OLU chromophores in the (A) S_0 and (B) S_1 electronic states and specific aminoacids of the enzyme along the MD trajectory.

To better understand the nature of the OLU/luciferase interactions, the direct hydrogen bonding between each OLU and each amino acid of the protein has been analyzed using the default cutoffs for hydrogen bonding implemented in *cpptraj*. Figure 8 represents the averaged amount of hydrogen bonds for those amino acids that present at least an average of 0.1 of hydrogen bonds in at least one of the studied systems. In general, the OLU chromophores do not present a high amount of direct hydrogen bonding with the protein. In the S_0 , the phenolate-keto form presents some hydrogen bonding between the O atom of the thiazole moiety and GLY318 ; the phenol-keto form, between the O atom of the benzothiazole moiety and SER316 and ARG339; the phenol-enolate form, between the O atom of the thiazole moiety and SER201, HIE247 and LYS531 and between the O atom of the benzothiazole moiety and SER316; and the phenolate-enolate form has hydrogen bonding between the O and N atoms of the benzothiazole and the O atom of the thiazole

moieties and ARG339, ALA350 and LYS531, respectively. In contrast, in the S_1 state, the phenolate-keto form presents some hydrogen bonds between the O atom of the thiazole and the N atom of the benzothiazole moieties and HIE247 and SER349, respectively; the phenol forms have hydrogen bonding only with the SER316 but in an opposite ratio with respect to the S_0 , and the phenolate-enolate OLU presents hydrogen bonding between the O atom of the benzothiazole moiety and ARG339 and between the O atom of the thiazole moiety and SER349 and ALA350.

Figure 8: Average of H bonds between each of the four OLU chromophores in the (A) S_0 and (B) S_1 electronic states and specific amino acids of the enzyme along the MD trajectory

In addition to the direct hydrogen bonding with the luciferase, it is also crucial for the understanding of the interactions of the OLU with the protein to characterize the amount of bridging water molecules connecting the chromophore and the enzyme through hydrogen bonding. For this purpose, Figure 9 represents the percentage of time that a water molecule is acting as a hydrogen bond bridge between the chromophore and a specific amino acid. A protein residue is considered only if the interaction is present at least 20% of the simulation time. As it can be observed, each chromophore presents an unique hydrogen bond bridging

pattern with the luciferase and, in addition, this pattern is different for each electronic state. In the case of the phenolate-keto OLU in the S_0 state, there is a significant amount of hydrogen bond bridging with the ARG220 and the ASN231 through the O atom of the benzothiazole moiety and with the SER316 through the N atom of the thiazole moiety. The phenol-enolate chromophore presents a significant amount of water molecules acting as hydrogen bond bridge between ARG339 and the O atom of the benzothiazole moiety and a smaller amount between HIE247, SER316, GLY318, THR345 and THR529 and the O atom of the thiazole moiety, except for the SER316 which is connected via hydrogen bond bridging with the O atom of the benzothiazole moiety. Furthermore, the phenolate-enolate OLU has two very important hydrogen bond bridges connecting SER316 and THR529 with the O atom of the benzothiazole and the thiazole moieties, respectively. Moreover, the phenol-keto form does not have a very important hydrogen bond bridging pattern in the S_0 , even though in the excited state it presents relevant bridges connecting GLY248, ARG339 and SER349 with N or O atoms of the benzothiazole moiety. In the S_1 electronic state, the phenolate-keto OLU presents an increased amount of hydrogen bond bridging with the SER316 with respect to the S_0 but through a different OLU heteroatom, the O atom of the benzothiazole moiety. Moreover, hydrogen bond bridging with ARG220 and ASN231 completely disappears and it is replaced with additional hydrogen bond bridges between SER203, HIE247, GLY318, ARG339 and THR529 and the O atoms of the thiazole moiety except for ARG339, that presents the hydrogen bond with the O atom of the benzothiazole moiety. In addition to the relevant bridging with ARG339 that the phenol-enolate presents in the ground state, in the S_1 this chromophore shows a larger hydrogen bond bridging pattern. Relevant contributions appear linking GLY248, GLY318, THR345 and SER349 with different hydrogen bond acceptors of the chromophore. In the case of the phenolate-enolate in the S_1 , the hydrogen bond bridging pattern is produced mostly between the hydrogen bond acceptors of the benzothiazole moiety and ARG220, ASN231 and GLU313. In general terms, it can be observed that all the studied OLUs presents a larger bridging pattern in the S_1 state

than in the ground state, except for the phenolate-enolate chromophore, mostly due to extra bridging points with the O atom of the thiazole moiety and the N atom of the benzothiazole one.

Figure 9: Percentage of time with a water molecule acting as a hydrogen bond bridge between each of the four OLU chromophores in the (A) S_0 and (B) S_1 electronic states and specific aminoacids of the enzyme along the MD trajectory.

The role of AMP

Finally, it is interesting to analyze the role of the AMP co-factor inside the active site. As it can be observed in Figure 10(A,B), the distance between the center of mass of the OLU and the AMP oscillates between 7.5 and 11 Å. However, it does not correlate with the interaction with the chromophore (Figure 10(C-F)). In the ground state, AMP presents a large amount of direct hydrogen bonding with the O atom of the thiazole moiety of both

phenolate ligands, while it requires an intermediate water molecule to interact with both hydrogen bond acceptors of the thiazole moiety of the phenol-enolate OLU. In the excited state, none of the chromophores present a significant hydrogen bonding with the AMP co-factor and only the phenolate-keto and the phenol-enolate are able to interact with the AMP via hydrogen bond bridging through the O atom of the thiazole moiety.

Figure 10: (A,B) Distance between the OLU chromophore to the AMP co-factor, (C,D) average of H bonds between each of the four OLU chromophores and the AMP and (E,F) percentage of time with a water molecule acting as a H bond bridge between each of the four OLU chromophores and the AMP for the MD trajectories in the (A,C,D) S_0 and (B,D,F) S_1 electronic states of each chromophore.

Conclusions

Fireflies' bioluminescent system has drawn a huge attention from the scientific community since it was first characterized. It is its high applicability as biosensor that has led to the publication of a wide variety of studies, and yet there are still a lot of unknowns, such as the OLU emitting form and the factors that affect the fine tuning of the emitted radiation. In this work, we present an extensive structural and intermolecular interaction analysis on

two different biological environments, water solvation and the luciferase enzyme, of the four possible emitting forms of the OLU in both ground and first electronically excited state. This work employs the recently published OLUFF to sample the conformational space of the different chromophores by MD simulations in order to determine their flexibility around the SCCS torsion, and to characterize the intermolecular interactions with the water molecules and protein residues through contact and hydrogen bonding analyses.

In aqueous media, the OLU presents similar probability distribution around the SCCS dihedral angle than that presented in a previous work³⁹ in gas phase due to a large flexibility for this degree of freedom. However, inside the active site the movement is sterically constrained and the chromophores can only populate the region near the *s*-trans conformation. The phenol-keto OLU in the ground state presents an exception to this. At the beginning of the simulation, it leaves the *s*-trans conformation to populate the *s*-cis configuration of the SCCS torsion, where it is trapped for the whole analyzed simulation time.

When looking at the solvation of the hydrogen bond acceptor atoms of the OLU in aqueous media, the larger the negative atomic charge on the heteroatom, the larger the solvation. On the flip side, in the pocket of the protein, the reduced amount of water molecules leads to a lower solvation. Moreover, the solvation pattern is different from that obtained in water, as a result of the competition with direct interactions with the protein and AMP, including hydrogen bonding and bridging interactions through water molecules. In addition, non-electrostatic interactions are also analyzed by a contact analysis, where the relevant aminoacids have been identified. Specifically, PHE249 has been shown to be the most relevant residue for both electronic states of the chromophores.

The results shown here could be the basis for future computational or experimental work aimed at mutating the luciferase enzyme to modify the behavior of the chromophores inside the pocket, and potentially control its emitting properties. However, to achieve such a challenging goal, further research is needed to understand first the influence of the variation of hydrogen bonding and contact patterns on the photophysics of the system.

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Supporting Information Available

Input files of the MD simulations and additional analysis are shown in the Supporting Information. Moreover, all the necessary input, topology, and initial coordinates files in Amber format, and all analysis data necessary to generate the represented figures in this manuscript can be found in the Zenodo repository DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.15132416.

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